

Understanding Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in the Workplace, What has Changed? - Literature Review

Richard Tumedisio*¹

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6310-9458>,
University of Zambia, Lusaka, Zambia P O Box 503691, Gaborone, Botswana

Dr. Abubaker Qutieshat*²,

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3569-6576>
Oman Dental College (ODC), P O Box 835, Mina Al Fahal, Muscat, Wattayah 116, Oman.
ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Abubaker_Qutieshat

Corresponding Author:- Richard Tumedisio*¹

Abstract:- The study assesses changes that have occurred to date with regard to diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) in the workplace and exploring ways of adopting DEI in a sustainable way. The study follows a systematic desk top research and techniques methodology to review existing literature on DEI in the workplace. Findings of the research are that time factor is a crucial component of Diversity, Equity & Inclusion (DEI) adoption. Interpretations of DEI are dynamic, they need continuous listening and learning. DEI as a performance tool allows the power of one individual to influence a group's social majority as objectivity takes precedence. DEI is the gateway to breakthrough innovation and is a building block to a better workplace. A practical implication of this research is that time is a critical factor in keeping up with DEI doctrine dynamics, keeping DEI relevant and continuously pursuing DEI phenomenon so that its benefits are well understood, appropriately incorporated, and sustainably managed. The research limitations are that organizational stakeholders best placed to promote adoption of DEI in the workplace have not been identified. Further studies are recommended to appreciate DEI impact at industry, geographical and individual employee level in line with organizational success.

Keywords:- Diversity; Equality; Equity; Exclusion; Identity; Inclusion and Workplace.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ *The Objectives of the Study are to Establish the following.*

- *Current views of DEI in the workplace.*
- *Achievements organizations have made regarding adopting DEI in the workplace.*
- *Opportunities available to adopt DEI in the workplace.*
- *Sustainable ways of adopting DEI in the workplace.*
- *DEI trends for organizations to look out for in future.*

The premise of the study is that human capital increases productivity which leads to profitability of an organization. Human capital is the driving force for sustainable growth of an organization. People lead in organizational activities including areas where robots and artificial intelligence are deployed, most importantly original plans come from a human being. One avenue in which the organization can foster participation of people to organizational success is adopting DEI on institutional and social processes of the organization hence the approach taken by this study to assess DEI in the workplace.

Cubas-Díaz & Martínez Sedano (2018) observe that the traditional investor relied on profit and risk as main factors to make investment decisions. Maximizing profits, reducing costs and mitigating risks were taken as the most important business goals. In the wake of multiple economic setbacks, the firm has had to find new ways of being effective. The new ways include being efficient with regard to use of resources including human capital for sustainability purposes. In addition, depletion of natural resources requires the firm to be innovative in using remaining resources whilst ensuring that the firm maintains competitiveness and remains financially sustainable.

Whilst Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is key in maximizing shared value between the firm and its stakeholders as acknowledged by Trivellas, Rafailidis, Polychroniou, & Dekoulou (2018), firms now talk of new performance metrics like Environmental, Social and Corporate Governance (ESCG) which deepen institutional theory on bench marking and reporting. Theorists Rabaya & Saleh (2022) indicate that these new approaches to performance measurement are efforts to cope with the new firm challenges and incorporating new findings to be part of reformed organizational performance strategies. With sustainability dominating new goals for management, business share values, business performance and sustainable practices have a mutual relationship.

Rabaya & Saleh (2022) have established that integrated reporting (IR) allows for integration of resources or capital as input, the business model as a process and results as value creation for organizational stakeholders. Thus, IR assists financiers to appreciate how the organization they are funding creates value over time. This view is shared by Aboud & Diab (2018) who posit that firms listed in the environmental and governance disclosures (ESG) have a higher firm value than firms which are not listed. Whilst acknowledging that although business assessments are fundamentally based on financial performance Vitolla, Raimo & Rubino (2019) refer to Alwert et al (2009) to emphasize that feedback on a firm's intangible assets is also key in determining a firm's value. Vitolla, Raimo & Rubino (2019) posit that the integrated thinking approach is able to link intellectual capital consisting of intellectual, human, social and relationship to other three types of capital namely financial, natural and manufactured. Thus, IR is a new way of determining how intangible resources and intellectual mix with physical resources. However, the advantages of IR are not guaranteed as Lebriz, Esch Wald & Heinzlmann (2019) warn that there is no evidence that ESG performance is higher for a firm using IR than one not using IR. The divergent findings leave room for more research to be conducted to inform the different schools of thought.

Gadinis & Miazad (2020) observe that sustainability performance requires firms to revisit their core business practices and in turn tailor make firm executive compensation to induce management to improve firm sustainability. Gadinis & Miazad (2020) warn that changes to firm practices to achieve sustainability is expensive in the short term. By defining business sustainability as adoption of business strategies and activities that address needs of the firm and its stakeholders today without compromising the same needs for other stakeholders in future Phan, Tran, Le, Nguyen, Pervan & Tran (2020) help to shed more light on where the short term expenses arise by citing examples of firm stakeholder practices where shareholders may choose to align with socially responsible investment, catering for employees whose interests may revolve around training and wage negotiations, customers who may value environmentally friendly products and the community who may value a firm that has better community services, participating in environmental programs and partnering with community members. All these identified provisions require the organization to allocate resources in the form of human, materials, monetary or capital and therefore incurring costs to have them in place.

In addition to Environmental Social and Governance disclosures giving a firm a higher value a study by Albitar, Hussainey, Kolade & Gerged (2020) indicates that the growing significance of sustainability to economic development has also advanced non-financial disclosures to the fore. Albitar et al (2020) refer to Akisik and Gal (2011) to emphasize that sustainable development is not only related to corporate social responsibility (CSR) and accounting standards but is also associated with customer satisfaction. Albitar et al (2020) reflect on observations by Kimbro & Cao (2011) and Li et al (2019) that past studies

have been looking at the impact of CSR on firm value or socially responsible investing (SRI) but have not covered sustainability and integrated reporting.

When fusing together research shortcomings identified by Albitar et al (2020) on need to focus on sustainability and integrated reporting and Phan et al (2020) statement for sustainable development practice (SDP) to go beyond short-term profitability one theory that brings a more relational concept which this study attempts to look into is diversity. Blom, du Plessis, & Kazeroony (2021) posit that the global changes require firms to come up with strategies and diversity presents itself as a critical driving force for change. Blom, du Plessis, & Kazeroony (2021) also adopt a research strategy that moves away from traditional diversity elements like race, ethnicity and language to a more all-encompassing and benevolent approach to organizational change. But Creary, Rothbard & Scruggs (2021) advise that promotion of diversity alone is insufficient and requires inclusion and belonging adding that diversity, equity and inclusion enhances wellness. Therefore, this study seeks to encourage organizations to take advantage of opportunities presented by adoption of DEI phenomenon in a continuous manner to address societal needs, meet customer expectations and at the same time generate profit in order to make the effort of DEI adoption sustainable.

II. BACKGROUND

A study by Gutterman (2021) highlights that work is a basic right that is recognized by nations and businesses through policies. However, Gutterman (2021, p.10) confirms earlier observations by theorists that this protected core labour rights do not enjoy the same treatment across the globe. The right to choose type of employment, freedom from conditions of work, freedom of association, equal pay for equal work, fair progression through organizational ranks, accommodation for personal needs like length of working hours, leave days and holidays do not all apply to all employees in the same way. This variation of work-related treatment contributes to the much-contested exclusions experienced in the workplace. Thus, organizations are not able to hire all job seekers, the patterns of hiring and career progression are found not fair and reasonable. Gutterman (2021,p.15) highlights the right to work by citing theorists Rodríguez-Pinzón and Martín (2003) who consider work as a right to earn a living and that the right must be accompanied by favourable work conditions with right to personal freedom and dignity. Work is considered a socio-economic and basic social, economic and cultural human right. The United Nations through the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) views the right to work as being fundamental to enjoying other human rights and to be deep rooted in human dignity.

Gutterman (2021,p.9) posits that part of formation of the International Labour Organization (ILO) constitution in the 1920s was to advocate for workers' rights which included amongst others favourable work conditions. In addition, related joint pledges continue to be made at global

level. In September 2015 world leaders adopted Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) which cover promoting inclusive decent work.

Calls for work to be considered a human right set a tone for all employers to change their work environment to accommodate issues of diversity, equity and inclusion. According to Gutterman (2021) organizations need to collect data on recruitment, promotions, remunerations and related issues that may be creating bias so that they can identify and accordingly change their processes to create the desired work environment. The argument is that failure to collect data creates information vacuum on problems existing on diversity, gender or racial gaps in remuneration and other work-related conditions. Although this data collection is not a simple matter it has impactful results. Gutterman (2021) advises that when diversity and inclusion are incorporated in a firm's mission with specific goals it will enable handling of diversity and inclusion in a transparent manner to fulfil purposes of visible organizational road map and corporate social responsibility framework for the firm.

The World Bank report (2019,p.4) states that work processes are dynamic due to technological developments and global interconnectedness. Production methods change, the market grows, people change and so do their preferences. Some changes create more exigent situations than others as a result of the degree of uncertainty involved. In this regard two global changes that can be related with are the 2008 global economic meltdown and of recent outbreak of Covid-19 both of which brought uncertainty and collapse of the global economy. (The World Bank report, 2019) Uncertainty manifested itself as the world got exposed to non-quantifiable risk because the extent of the two major changes could not be established and neither could it be predicted. What followed after the global meltdown and Covid-19 pandemic was collapse of business activities with many organizations getting pushed into financial distress.

The one lesson that comes out of both the economic meltdown and Covid-19 outbreak crisis is that changes in the global market cannot be accurately predicted and prepared for. At the moment the world is witnessing yet another worrying global impacting development in Europe where Russia is at war and trying to occupy Ukraine. Rhee et al (2022) observe that the Russian war on Ukraine has not helped the world to effectively recover from Covid-19 pandemic. According to Rhee et al (2022) Russia and Ukraine are major commodity producers, and their war has spiked prices for basic needs like oil, natural gas and wheat noting that Ukraine and Russia contribute 30% of global wheat exports. Kammer et al (2022) identify three main channels the Russian-Ukraine war is impacting on namely, the high commodity prices rising inflation, neighbouring nations having to deal with disruptions in trade processes and lastly tarnished business confidence and investor uncertainty in the affected region. At organizational level the economic meltdown, Covid-19 pandemic and Russia-Ukraine war disruptions demonstrate negative developments that can impact the workplace and highlight that there is no

single solution for all organizational problems and that laws can only go so far in addressing some industry challenges. On the other hand, rethinking ways of adopting DEI especially as a source of organizational solutions instead of conforming to agreements underscore the importance of engaging a diverse work force to deal with complex organizational challenges.

III. METHODOLOGY

This is an exploratory study that adopts a desk top research and techniques approach to understand diversity, equity and inclusion in the workplace. The reason for the desk research approach is based on existing literature that the topic pursued is relatively new and dynamic. It will be helpful to piece together what other scholars have independently established, and state findings to appreciate current views and establish emerging patterns as DEI phenomenon evolves.

DEI phenomenon has its history relating to civil rights movement but with time has evolved to firm level where its interpretation has also evolved to cater for organizational objectives. This study adopts a systematic desktop research and techniques approach to review existing literature on DEI in the workplace. Organizational performance matrices like Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Environmental Social and Governance disclosures (ESCG) and non-financial disclosures have been established as being effective in determining an organization's sustainability.

On the other hand, strategies to improve adoption of organizational performance matrices rely on the human resource for knowledge building and effectively implement the performance matrices. As the study explores existing literature the study converges ideas and identifies opportunities that the organizational environment presents to optimize benefits of adopting DEI and also identify trends for organizations to explore in future to further improve sustainable organizational operations. Relevant literature is purposively selected by using key search words, the workplace, identity, exclusion, equality, diversity, equity and inclusion.

➤ *Sampling*

The information collected is sought through Google Scholar, Elsevier database and associated business journals all of which have been published within the last five years save for articles defining fundamental concepts and processes. The study keywords are Diversity, Equity and Inclusion are used to choose relevant literature. Choosing the most recent publications taps into varying thoughts on trending DEI issues and converges useful thoughts that can be handy in gainful application and composing organizational performance improvement strategies relevant to today's organizations. For definitions and related theories keywords are used individually and with other words such as meaning, compliance, trends and history.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selected journals and publications are used to construct themes to guide the study. Firstly, key words are defined, schools of thought relating to DEI phenomenon are identified, lessons around the phenomenon are explored with the aim of identifying take home notes and areas that need further studying.

➤ *Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Framework*

Research has built knowledge to better appreciate DEI. Arsel, Crockett & Scott (2022, p.1) offer research specific definitions for DEI as follows; diversity is generally actual or recognized physical or socio-psychological incongruity tied to people and how this difference is portrayed in the field of research, organizations and the market space. Koellen (2021,p.3) borrows from (Gardenswartz & Rowe, 1998; Klarsfeld, Ng, Booysen, Christiansen, & Kuvaas, 2016) to add that diversity can be understood in a variety of ways including sharing with one another or differing from each other due to a specific establishment of a characteristic. This definition ties with general theory that diversity can be understood in terms of race, age, cultural background, sexual orientation, gender and faith. Diversity by virtue of bringing different people together cultivates a culture of providing different ideas on work approaches, improves workforce effectiveness and objectivity. Authors Arsel, Crockett and Scott (2022, p.1) define Equity as reasonableness on opportunity and outcomes treatment. It therefore follows that reasonableness in the workplace accords every worker equal opportunity, everyone is informed about what is happening within the organization with respect to what is expected of them in return for what they expect from the workplace. Equity ensures that every worker is treated as and feels like a stakeholder in an organization's proceedings. Equity notes that people need to be assisted differently according to their unique positions in order to ensure uniformity in terms of assisting individuals to remain in par within an organization. Arsel, Crockett and Scott (2022, p1) define inclusion as promoting a culture that enables association and absorption of diverse groups in operations. It can therefore be concluded that inclusion opens up to people's differences and promotes a sense of belonging for employees with regard to the workplace. Inclusion does not bind anyone to change their approach in order to fit in the workplace. Inclusion pays no attention to an employee's personal circumstances.

However, Arsel, Crockett & Scott. (2022, p1) highlight that the definitions above are limited to specific research and this underscores appreciation that this is a young field that still needs more research in order to mature. The take home notes deduced from arguments advanced by Arsel, Crockett & Scott. (2022) are that DEI should be studied by various stakeholders as solutions identified by one party may not necessarily work for the other due to possible varying understanding of the DEI phenomenon. This view underscores the importance of researching more on DEI to identify different avenues available to successfully incorporate DEI in different organizations and in different environments.

➤ *Future Life Outlook*

In demonstrating how important it is for society to make use of all strategies available to manage resources Fry & Egel (2021,p.3) warn about the speed at which society is exhausting natural resources. Fry and Egel (2021,p.3) refer to a report by Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2013) which states that the world is using 50% more natural resources than the rate at which planet earth can recover, 30% of the world population lacks clean water and at this rate by 2050 society will need 2,9 planets to sustain life. The report warns that the world needs new leadership that will address the economic, social and environmental issues on sustainability also known as the triple bottom line. These three pillars indicate social, financial and environmental health of a business over time.

➤ *Linking Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion*

Theorists' warnings about a bleak future suggest that efforts to avoid the catastrophe should start soon. At organizational level adopting DEI may yield positive results. But how do the three terms diversity, equity and inclusion relate? In linking diversity, equity and inclusion Korn Ferry.com starts by acknowledging that the biggest challenge is to create growth, and that growth is achieved through differentiation, in turn differentiation needs innovation. Innovation thrives in the presence of diversity and diversity needs inclusion in order to embrace different people's ideas in the organization. The presence of diverse people in the workplace requires an inclusive leadership to tap into DEI for improving organizational performance. Therefore, DEI is not just about according to people's rights to work but a symbiotic relationship that accords both the firm and society to thrive through a give and take relationship.

The work environment is affected by social dynamics within society. Social dynamics in society are in turn impacted upon by identity politics. It therefore follows that managing changes from organizational level can in turn influence society. Based on views around DEI and its relationship with productivity and economics one way of appreciating dynamics of DEI is to look at its history through the lens of country economies. The lens of developed and developing nations offers a platform to assess how DEI has evolved. Shore, Cleveland and Sanchez (2018,p.1) are quick to point out that advances in life have given birth to globalization which is characterized by boundaryless and virtual organizations which again call for new theories to create literature that relates to the present situation. Al Ariss (2010) underscores the importance of understanding diversity, equity and inclusion in the context of time in order to appreciate the history, the present and predict the future. Al Ariss (2010) observes that in management research diversity context is omitted and this leads to knowledge gaps in institutional, cultural and national issues. Arguments by Al Ariss (2010) tie with recommendations by Gutterman (2021) that narrowing down DEI to specific goals instead of generalizing enable handling of diversity and inclusion in a more beneficial way. Being specific helps in addressing each challenge or problem specifically with organizational road map outlined and

corporate social responsibility framework for the firm with regard to DEI clearly stipulated.

➤ *Brief Historical Views on Diversity Issues*

Shore, Chung-Herrera, Dean, Ehrhart, Jung, Randel & Singh (2009) posit that diversity has historically been treated in a reactive approach where diversity related issues were managed as and when they emerged indicating that in research and practice words used to describe diversity impact on how the phenomenon is treated. Ballard, Allen, Ashcraft, Ganesh, McLeod & Zoller (2020) offer a new line of argument emphasizing the importance of moving away from just words and suggesting influencers to focus more on actions as potential sources of power and potential to effect change. Ballard et al (2020) also indicate that diversity research has progressed from addressing social injustice issues like exclusion of certain sections of society to exploiting diversity for economic gains.

Sabattini (2020) adds that in practice organizations are exploring future work that is flexible, caters for social justice, privilege in order to improve prospects of business performance. Researchers also follow suit as observed by Ballard et al (2020) that research has moved from analysing inclusion processes to economic outcomes like group task performance and company financial performance. Likewise relying on quotas for compliance purposes will not necessarily create that enabling environment for DEI to flourish but instead Ballard et al (2020) recommend enabling environment like having group task performance which engages different team members to utilize their multiple and potentially complementary skills to realize organizational goals. This stance also supersedes previous literature points of focus like those identified by Nkomo et al (2019) as being more focused on understanding experiences of exclusion more than knowing processes, practices and mechanisms that promote equality and inclusion in the workplace.

Freeman (2020) offers a link and importance of previous studies and recommendations. Instead of doing away with past recommendations Freeman (2020) argues their importance and possible complementary use like an organization that measures its degree of DEI adoption can for instance determine the impact of DEI on the business's ability to understand its target customers by matching the degree of employee representing the target market in terms of race, gender, age or culture.

➤ *Trends in Developed Nations*

Shore, Cleveland and Sanchez (2018,p.1) indicate that in the developed economy of United States of America (USA) there is history of social exclusion and economic inequality in the workplace. The authors cite exclusion along race and ethnic lines, aged workers, sexual orientation and gender identity, religion and disabled people. Rosenkranz et al (2021, p.1) posit that diversity value has been appreciated following its studies in the 1990s and 2000s especially by corporate bodies who adopted it through culture and strategy. Some theorists argue that the issue of exclusion dates back as far back as the 1940s when men

went to war and in the interest of maintaining business continuity women assumed some work assignments which were traditionally done by men.

The USA experience on diversity is given by Rosenkranz et al (2021, p.1) who state that diversity was established in the 1960s through anti-discriminatory laws which prompted leaders in the army, local communities, employers and educators to educate their members as a way of alleviating the negative impact of discrimination and compliance to standards.

Köllen (2019, p.2) confirms diversity developments in USA by stating that affirmative action which was fundamentally introduced to curb racial and gender discrimination started losing steam in the 1980s. This gave diversity management an opportunity to establish itself. Whilst it served purposes of promoting inclusion, diversity management proved to be inclined to organizational profits. At the time the value of diversity was not acknowledged, and this only changed in the 1990s and 2000s when the phenomenon matured. According to Rosenkranz et al (2021,p.1) adoption of diversity and inclusion in the workplace through culture and strategy did not only improve relationships but increased problem-solving potential, compatibility within teams, reduced staff turnover and increased employee engagement. In addition, organizational boards which are more diverse earn more profits and generally perform better than their competitors. The findings are supported by Velasco and Sansone (2019, p.2) who highlight that firms that embrace diversity earn higher profits and are more innovative. But Velasco and Sansone (2019,p.2) borrow from Garr (2014) to point out DEI related challenges stating that whilst many North American firms desire an inclusive organizational culture only a few have provisions in place.

➤ *Trends in Developing Nations.*

According to Ohunakin et al (2019,p.3) whilst in USA there were affirmative actions from civil right movement to stop cultural and racial exclusion, in Australia affirmative action programs were fighting gender exclusion. Ohunakin, F., Adeniji, A. A., Ogunnaike, O. O., Igbadume, F., & Akintayo, D. I. (2019,p3) refers to observations by Jayne and Dipboye (2004) that besides diversity management being broad there are a number of programs that address critical areas like recruitment, promotion and retention to include diverse groups. Ohunakin et al (2019, p4) refers to a study by Ortlieb and Sieben (2014) who argue that inclusion is a new phenomenon with limited literature on it and no standard definition. According to (Cilliers, 2007) as quoted by Setati, S.T., Zhuwao, S., Ngirande, H. and Ndlovu, W. (2019,p.1) exclusion in South Africa in the region of Africa where before the official end of apartheid era in 1994, there were social and political boundaries that separated people through gender, race, institutional and spatial inequalities. Setati.et al (2019,p1) observe that whilst diversity adoption has risen prejudice, discrimination and sexual harassment still exist in South Africa. Setati.et al (2019,p1) relates the source of the problem as emanating from a belief leaders

hold that diversity is a legal issue and not a valuable tool for organizational effectiveness.

Klarsfeld et al (2019,p.3) indicate that after getting insightful literature from South Korea, Ethiopia, the Caribbean, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Bangladesh they concluded that in many nations excluded groups comprised of women, disabled people and issues of racial and ethnic origin had an influence. In a study done in Kenya, Ali (2019, p.10) established that employee recruitment and selection does impact on diversity management therefore organizations must develop and adopt recruitment and policies that embrace diversity.

➤ *DEI globally*

Roberts, Washington and Felix. (2020, p.3) illuminate a trend that is playing out at organizational level does happen at a larger scale when looking at regional economic blocks. Roberts, Washington and Felix (2020, p3) point out that in spite of globalization and trade growing substantially, the rewards have not been evenly distributed. An example is given that the share of African exports in the intra-African exports grew to 17% but this is low when looking at ratios of other regions like Europe standing at 69%, Asia 59% and North America at 31%. Roberts, Washington and Felix (2020,p3) give additional examples of exclusion where they for instance challenge absence of a USA (developed economy) – Africa (developing economy) summit indicating that some regions like the European Union hold summits with African presidents and leaders. Summits are recognised for providing countries and other economic players a platform to interact and advance national issues of interests. Bodies like the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement are meant to speed up export diversification and promote inclusive trading.

Putman & Byker (2020) refer to Byker (2016) to posit that through advances in technology and ever-expanding networks people across the globe are connected electronically and face-to-face. Inegbedion et al (2020,p.3) argue that literature on diversity management is limited to business efficiency with previous studies establishing that exclusion due to sexual orientation, ethnic differentiation, age, fear of change and communication barriers impede realization of workforce diversity. As a result, adaptability is slow, there are limited problem-solving techniques and limited skills and experiences.

• *DEI in the Industry -Lessons from the World Bank*

The World Bank has a code of ethics that are expressive of core values in practice and are pivoted more on conduct than conformity. The World Bank has a guide to assist management and staff in making an inclusive, values-based workplace with special attention to disability, LGBT+ and mental well-being. World Bank (2022) has gained a second level of Economic Dividends for Gender Equality (EDGE) certification. The certification enables actual measurement of milestones on equal pay for equivalent work, recruitment and promotion, leadership development training and mentoring, flexible working arrangements and company culture. The World Bank has a moderated

anonymous online discussion which enable staff to share suggestions and views.

V. LESSONS AND MILESTONES ASSOCIATED WITH DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION

In a study carried by (Hossain et al,2020), it is appreciated that there is positive impact brought by changes that occurred at the United Nations level where in 2017 the High Commissioner for human rights unveiled new codes of conduct to reduce exclusion of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender (LGBT) in the work environment. The new codes of conduct have public and financial impact. Hossain et al (2020, p.2) borrow from Liddle et al (2004) to demonstrate that when LGBT employees are officially recognized they will be more at ease and financially improve organizational outcomes. Financial benefits of welcoming LGBT employees in Australia can translate to as much as \$285 million per annum in the work environment countrywide, this will reverse staff turnover by 11% and add to productivity improvement by 30%. At operational level of firms pro-LGBT policies promise increase in talent pool and diversity level with innovation improvement going up by as much as 10%.

VI. PLANS AND AREAS TO INCORPORATE DEI

In a paper titled ‘Figuring Out Where to Start, and How’ Garcia and Calkins (2019) provide insights on areas where organizations can make meaningful changes in adopting diversity, equity and inclusion as follows.

➤ *Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in an Organization’s Business Case*

When incorporating DEI in an organization’s business case this sets the organization’s employees as individuals and teams to shift their norms and values towards DEI. The degree to which DEI is incorporated into business has to be measured in order to ascertain progress made. Freeman (2020,p.1) argues that disparities cannot be reduced if they cannot be measured.

Freeman (2020,p.1) decries lack of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Queer or Questioning (LGBTQ) demographic data indicating that it defeats appreciation and effort to address exclusion of LGBTQ community despite their crucial role in technological evolution. For instance, in USA, LGBTQ scientists played a key role in establishing artificial intelligence (AI) through Mathematician Alan Turing, central processing unit (cpu) through Engineer Lynn Conway and space travel through Sally Ride as the first female to travel to space.

According to Freeman (2020) LGBTQ data does get collected but is not openly shared citing observations by Freeman et al. (2018) that many surveys on the USA population have successfully collected Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) for many years. It is assumed that SOGI questions are intrusive in nature, but experience has proven that such sentiments are not consistent. Past population surveys show that SOGI measures do not result

in survey break off or high non-response rates, that the questions are similar to demographic questions and that the law still provides confidentiality of personal data therefore there is room to adopt SOGI measures on national data (Freeman et al. (2018).

➤ *Staff Recruitment and Engagement*

Ali (2019,p.10) advocates for advanced practices in interviewing, hiring, and handling of vacancy documentation and advertising in order to strengthen organizational human resource. Hiring approaches like psychometric tests can be explored with a view of matching candidates to vacancies as they objectively test a person's mental ability and personality.

According to Ali (2019,p.10) candidate recruitment and selection impact on diversity management. Diversity of employees can be achieved when recruitment and hiring procedures remove bias in language where no language is given unfair recognition over other languages, making job descriptions free from being sexist but instead focusing on job objectives and ensuring that interview questions go beyond just covering DEI issues but also seek DEI skills and awareness from job seekers.

Ali (2019,p.10) recommends formulation and implementation of favourable recruitment and selection policies to enhance diversity management. The broader context of diversity requires acknowledgement of differences in people and overcoming oppressive systems emanating from inequality brought about by people's bias due to their differences.

➤ *Employee Inclusion and Privilege*

Kuknor and Bhattacharya (2021,p.3) posit that inclusion influences employee engagement, job satisfaction, employee self-esteem and organizational citizenship behaviour. Kuknor and Bhattacharya (2021,.3) further draw lessons from Dymski (2010) to state that where there is inequality in the economy inclusion reduces the negative impact. Padamsee and Crowe (2017) warn organizations to differentiate inclusion from assimilation. Whilst both may appear good in promoting a high degree of belongingness with inclusion treating an individual as an insider but allowing an individual to retain their uniqueness, assimilation suppresses uniqueness and instead requires an individual to conform to an organizational or dominant culture.

There is an argument that supporting diversity and inclusion requires understanding of privilege. Geiger and Jordan (2014,p.4) indicate that there is limited study on the role of people with societal privilege when it comes to adopting inclusion. Privilege is basically a special right or advantage enjoyed by a person or a group of people and that which is not available to each and every one and is institutional. These aspects in the workplace enable those privileged to share their privilege thereby helping organizations to create sustainable jobs.

By sharing privilege organizational members being reached out to feel included and develop a sense of belonging to an organization. Martinescu, Jansen & Beersma (2021) add that it is critical for people to feel included as being socially included fulfills one's needs for belongingness and authenticity. Martinescu, Jansen & Beersma (2021) emphasize that when social engagement thrives people engage in positive social exchanges, extend their goodwill to others and achieve sustainable cooperation. Other advantages mentioned are that when cooperation is established organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is achieved and this in turn enables functioning of work groups. Martinescu, E., Jansen, W., & Beersma, B. (2021) explain that OCB encourages bonding between group members who in turn act in the best interests of the group with minimum force from outside. Thus, inclusion is strategically realized without appearing to be overly generous.

➤ *Other Avenues of Optimizing Benefits of DEI.*

There are other avenues of optimizing on benefits of promoting DEI which Padamsee and Crowe (2017) identify as follows.

• *Understanding of Organizational Customers.*

Padamsee and Crowe (2017,p.8) indicate that DEI firms have an appreciable understanding of communities they serve. This understanding helps the organization to accommodate customers in contributing to organizational strategies and priorities.

Specific practices and competencies on this phenomenon are empathy, understanding issues from a customer perspective and using that information to inform practice that incorporates customer needs, identifying and doing away with bias.

• *Increased Diversity of thought*

Promotion of varying perspectives of patterns of thought, ideas, problem-solving approaches inspire creativity and strengthen innovation. According to Padamsee and Crowe (2017, p.3) research has proven that organizations that have increased diversity of thought enjoy higher performance and the diverse team members are more innovative and more creative. On the opposite end being influenced by group think may make decision making easier but this introduces bias and people who may have different and viable ideas end up suppressing their contributions. In the end the organization loses out as workers concentrate on self-interest and tolerate wrongdoings.

• *Building Trusted Relationships.*

Padamsee and Crowe (2017, p.3) indicate that firms with high DEI are able to make and sustain trusted relationships. Prior to undertaking of tasks relationship building is necessary for laying the groundwork. Kulik (2022) borrow from Cristea & Leonardi (2019) to express the impact of trust in the workplace where in a trust-based work scenario the employer foregoes control of working time and instead measures worker performance against results. Reflecting on resumption of normal working hours

following advances made in the control of Covid 19 impact, Kulik (2022) touches on the need to move resumption of work to 'next normal' instead of 'new normal' arguing that the 'next normal' can adopt hybrid work models that combine the work from home that enables employees to spend some working hours at the office and other working hours at their homes carrying out job tasks. The hybrid model stresses employer trust on employees by according employees more control over their work hours which Kulik (2022) refers to findings by Henly & Lambert (2014) and Lyness et al (2021) that giving employees more control over their work hours improves employee commitment, improves stress levels and boosts worker autonomy. Kulik (2022) refers to findings by Lindzon (2021) to state that the hybrid model enables employee interactions which are highly valued by younger and early career employees.

Thus, the hybrid model caters for a wider range of worker preferences and improving relationships. Relationships are proven building blocks for organizing community activities as they are means for achieving goals and meaningfully contribute to building a better working environment to appeal to a wider range of potential employees. The hybrid model contributes to addressing earlier sentiments by Sabattini (2020) on future work being flexible. It follows that DEI adoption cuts across many spheres of the organization as it requires improved accountability and metrics that better reflect desired organizational culture.

➤ *DEI based Staff Retention Proposals.*

In a staff retention study Drake and McGee (2021,p.3) observes that University of Kansas Medical Centre has been striving to adopt diversity recruitment but did that through departmental silos. The study proposes a collaborative approach with staff retention suggestions covering fair and equitable remunerations and promotions, equal chances for growth and development, integrating cultural competency standards for organizational departments on an ongoing basis, connecting diverse organizational members with peer and departmental mentors through a formalized mentoring programme followed by collecting metrics and analysing to determine success of the strategy. Thus, an organization wide approach is recommended instead of a segmented approach as this may introduce inequalities.

In acknowledging generational shift in workforce and accommodating new generations who will soon play a key role in shaping society and industries Mahmoud et al (2021,p2) posits that organizations should communicate strong branding through new lines of communications like social media networks which generations Y and Z make use of like no other generation in the workplace. Mahmoud et al (2021,p2) acknowledges the critical roles played by each generation in the workplace and submits that a diverse generation workforce can be catered for by adopting agile methods in the workplace which will also overcome endless disruptions. According to Mahmoud et al (2021) when the organization caters for employees there are gains made on enhancing employees' morale, productivity and employee retention.

VII. OTHER AREAS WHERE DIVERSITY CAN MANIFEST ITSELF IN AN ORGANIZATION

According to Koellen (2021) social factors like demography, legal framework, socio-political issues and specific history determine diversity issues for every geographical workforce. Koellen (2021,p2) points out that different legal frameworks in different countries may create different proportions of diversity in workers found in a particular geographical area giving examples of how Austria and Germany having a somewhat similar approach to managing diversity. The approaches are having work life balance measures, having networks around diversity issues, empowering members of the discriminated groups, having relevant organizational ethics, creating awareness and having specific group marketing. This finding is supported by Andersen, L. L., Proper, K. I., Punnett, L., Wynne, R., Persson, R., & Wiezer, N. (2015,p.1-2) who state that the work environment differs partly due to aspects of geographical location, local rules and regulations, social support services, production processes and human capital systems in place.

VIII. OUTCOMES OF DIVERSITY EFFORTS

Diversity efforts face challenges that result in successes and failures. The following are successes and failures encountered in relation to adopting DEI.

➤ *Successes of Diversity Efforts*

Amongst diversity efforts that succeed as identified by Dobbin and Kalev (2016,p.10) are voluntary training, establishing self-managed teams, implementing cross training, college recruitment targeting underrepresented groups, having diversity task groups, mentoring and having diversity managers. The key lesson on positive outcomes is that relaxing controls, increasing contact amongst group members reduces resistance on adopting desired behaviour.

Other successes as identified by Lashitew, Bals and van Tulder (2020, p.36) are social change and contribution to business practice. Social change comes in increase in knowledge and awareness in establishing equity and fair management practice on characteristics affected by discriminatory measures. This will create a working environment that caters for employee needs and improved organizational performance. Contribution to business practice comes in the form of advancing understanding of diverse workforce management for new entrepreneurial and innovation strategies.

➤ *Failures in Diversity Efforts*

Velasco and Sansone (2019,pp.4-5) conclude by identifying three causes of diversity and inclusion intolerance as anxiety caused by fear of the unknown, perceived inequity due to fear of losing power and privilege and ostracism. Although Velasco and Sansone (2019,p.9) point to limited population of study as a weak point for their study this paper emphasizes that when well-developed questions are used high quality data can still be collected.

Dobbin and Kalev (2016, p.9) posit that diversity efforts that fail include mandatory diversity training, testing job candidates and having grievance procedures. On the surface having rules appear to straighten out issues to ensure compliance but in practice the provision sparks resistance as managers who are key in implementing ideas feel overcontrolled and end up implementing rules selectively or finding ways to get back to those appealing manager decisions through grievance procedures. A way of addressing this problem is to reduce complaints and prevent grievances whilst safeguarding institutional interests is to get all stakeholders to participate in decision making and problem solving so that there is collective ownership on actions taken. This observation is supported by Will, P. and Hamilton, O., (2021,p.2) who state that people instinctively resist forced ideas and rules due to emotions and belief in making one's own choices. Will and Hamilton (2021,p.2) recommend persuasion to be used to overcome the push back reaction and if done properly this approach will naturally support DEI initiatives. Thus, formulation of policies to try and change human behaviour is discouraged but instead use of persuasion is encouraged.

Ladwig (2021, p.5) states that on Trans and Gender Diversity (TGD) Western definition of sexual orientation and expression have an impact when similar research is carried out in the developing world. Prediction by sociologists that there will be more TGD people joining the workforce further supports the need to further explore the phenomenon in order to understand it better and work out how best to cope with and get the best out of it.

According to the City of Oshawa's handbook Lens (2021) Equity and. explains that aiming for equality may create inequities. Lens (2021, p.21) identifies pitfalls introduced by an organization that attempts to treat everyone equally. Equality by virtue of definition accords everyone the same amount of treatment or award and by so doing those who need less get excess and those who need more get less than they require resulting in inequity. On the other hand, equity ensures that everyone has access to equal results and benefits by treating individuals according to their unique needs and doing away with systematic barriers. Along with relating equity to DEI Lens (2021, p.21) mentions two other terms worth taking note of. These are oppression and privilege. Lens (2021,p.21) defines Oppression as a systematic discrimination that stems from prejudice and institutional power which give dominant group right or privilege over target groups on access to resources. Privilege as understood earlier is prevalent at individual level, between individuals, cultural and organizational level where dominant groups enjoy convenience, benefits and favours at the expense of subordination groups. The playing field is levelled by voluntarily sharing the privileges.

➤ *Future Challenges of Diversity*

The Deloitte Millennial Survey (2014, p.2) posits that in the 2025 the global workforce will comprise of millennials who will by then be in leadership positions. Whilst the earlier generation developed ethnicity and race

diversity measurements, millennials hold a different view and actually consider diversity as differences in experiences, backgrounds and individual views. This therefore raises questions on relevance of measuring race which theorists like Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik (2003) indicate as necessary for people who are geographically divided into large ethnic groups.

It can be noted that diversity on its own is not enough. A sense of belonging (inclusion) and experience of fairness (equity) are equally important. The three aspects of DEI work like tripod legs to carry the organization, failure of one aspect has a negative impact on the overall performance of the organization. The impact of Environmental, Social and corporate Governance (ESCG) mentioned earlier is confirmed by Li, Gong, Zhang and Koh (2018) who state that the firm can increase its value by being more transparent, being more accountable and improving stakeholder trust.

There is also a need for mind set change. A growing interest in human behaviour has established that people think and process information differently and this should not disadvantage those who are found to be different from majority. A study by Austin and Pisano (2017) argues that people are like puzzle pieces, people are literally irregular and people's information processing is either neurotypical or neurodivergent. Neuro typical refers to people whose brain processing and behaviour is considered typical or standard and neuro divergent are those whose thinking, behaviour and learning is different from what is considered normal. Austin and Pisano (2017) observe that whilst neuro divergent people unemployment may be as high as 80% well-known companies like Microsoft, Hewlett Packard Enterprise Company (HPE) and Systems Applications and Products (SAP) revised their human resources processes to hire neurodiverse people. As a separate study it will be interesting to establish if there is a meaningful explanation why all the three firms are technological businesses. Sherman (2017) highlights that tech companies have faced public criticism in the past and began publishing diversity adoption efforts which indicate improvement in embracing diverse workforce. However, a closer look at the results reveals statistics based on employee surveys only which are prone to bias therefore there is still a long way to go in embracing diversity. This perspective emphasizes an earlier argument which referred to Gutterman (2021) advising firms to collect work related data in order to address shortfalls.

IX. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Conducting literature review revealed the extent to which DEI can be explored for the benefits of both the public and the firm. This study has identified benefits of adopting Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) in the workplace, but additional research is needed to further relate the benefits to geographical, specific industry and other differentiating elements which are necessary in assimilating DEI to appropriate situations.

Owing to the dynamic definition of DEI phenomenon it follows that excluded groups are likely to be different from the traditionally identified groups and continuous studies will help in keeping pace with the optimization of DEI adoption on organizational performance.

The study established that inclusion is hard to measure but could not identify ways of measuring inclusion. Critical areas like organizational supply chains can be pursued further to assess how an organization can influence its supply chains to promote DEI adoption.

X. CONCLUSION

Whilst observing a right to work, the doctrine of management prerogative accords an employer a right to use their discretion to hire, assign, supervise, terminate employment and recall employees in order to protect a firm's right to return of investment. Coupled with labour laws to monitor and regulate employment the two views send the employer and employee on a collision course. However, DEI phenomenon takes no sides on who is right and who is wrong but instead suggests persuasion as a winning formula for the employer and employee to optimize outcomes of their employer-employee relationship. There is a challenge also thrown in that if inclusion and equity are achieved there should be a way of making them sustainable over time. Thus, for policy makers, instead of formulating policies aimed at changing human behaviour the use of persuasion to gain buy-in from targeted stakeholders and adoption of Environmental, Social and corporate Governance (ESCG) are new organizational performance matrices which need firm transparency and accountability in order to gain and improve organizational stakeholder trust.

Understanding of DEI necessitated looking at historical background of the phenomenon and its current form has more common factors than before due to global interconnectedness. There are now more universal approaches to DEI adoption. DEI as a performance tool allows the power of one individual to influence a group's social majority as objectivity takes precedence. Time factor has been identified as a crucial component of DEI adoption, improving organizational performance needs new ways of seeing and understanding issues.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Aboud, A., & Diab, A. (2018). The impact of social, environmental and corporate governance disclosures on firm value: Evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*.
- [2]. Al Ariss, A. (2010) Book Review. Equality, Diversity and Inclusion at Work: A Research Companion. *Personnel Review*, 39 (5) 674-677
- [3]. Albitar, K., Hussainey, K., Kolade, N., & Gerged, A. M. (2020). ESG disclosure and firm performance before and after IR: The moderating role of governance mechanisms. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-09-2019-0108>
- [4]. Ali, M. (2019). Influence of recruitment and selection of diversity management amongst state corporations in Mombasa County. *ISSN 2312-9492*
- [5]. Andersen, L. L., Proper, K. I., Punnett, L., Wynne, R., Persson, R., & Wiezer, N. (2015). Workplace health promotion and wellbeing. *Scientific World Journal*, 2015, 606875.
- [6]. Appel-Meulenbroek, H. A. J. A., Vosters, S. M. C., Kemperman, A. D. A. M., & Arentze, T. A. (2019, January). Workplace needs and their support are millennials different from other generations. In *Proceedings of the Twenty Fifth Annual Pacific Rim Real Estate Society Conference (PRRES 2019), Melbourne, Australia* (pp. 14-16).
- [7]. Arsel, Z., Crockett, D., & Scott, M. L. (2022). Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in the Journal of Consumer Research: A Curation and Research Agenda. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 48(5), 920-933. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jcr/ucab057/6371980>
- [8]. Austin, R. D., & Pisano, G. P. (2017). Neurodiversity as a competitive advantage. *Harvard Business Review*, 95(3), 96-103.
- [9]. Ballard, D., Allen, B., Ashcraft, K., Ganesh, S., McLeod, P., & Zoller, H. (2020). When words do not matter: Identifying actions to effect diversity, equity, and inclusion in the academy. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 34(4), 590-616. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0893318920951643>
- [10]. Blom, T., du Plessis, Y., & Kazeroony, H. H. (2021). Enabling Sustainable Organizational Change: A Case of Cognitive Diversity in the Automotive Industry. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 20(1), 7. 10.5 <https://doi.org/590/IJAMT.2021.20.1.08>
- [11]. Creary, S. J., Rothbard, N., & Scruggs, J. (2021). Improving workplace culture through evidence-based diversity, equity and inclusion practices.
- [12]. Cubas-Díaz, M., & Martínez Sedano, M. A. (2018). Measures for sustainable investment decisions and business strategy—a triple bottom line approach. *Business strategy and the environment*, 27(1), 16-38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1980>
- [13]. Deloitte, T. (2014). Big demands and high expectations: The Deloitte millennial survey. *DTTL Global Brand & Communications*
- [14]. Dobbin, F., & Kalev, A. (2016). Why Diversity Programs fail. *Harvard Business Review*, 94(7), 14.
- [15]. Drake, R. L., & McGee, J. (2021). Recruitment and Retention Plan Proposal.
- [16]. Freeman, J. B. (2020). Measuring and resolving LGBTQ disparities in STEM. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 7(2), 141-148. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732220943232>

- [17]. Fry, L. W., & Egel, E. (2021). Global Leadership for Sustainability. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 6360. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116360>
- [18]. Gadinis, S., & Miazad, A. (2020). Corporate Law and Social Risk. *Vand. L. Rev.*, 73, 1401.
- [19]. Garcia, C., & Calkins, A. D. (2019). Figuring out where to start, and how: one library's DEI strategies. <https://doi.org/10.7710/1093-7374.1988>
- [20]. Gutterman, A. (2021) Human Rights of Older Persons. *Human Rights of Older Persons (Oakland CA: Ageism Project, 2021)*.
- [21]. Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, J. H. (2003). Regional Influences on Attitudes Toward Foreigners. In *Germans or Foreigners? Attitudes Toward Ethnic Minorities in Post-Reunification Germany* (pp. 255-268). Palgrave Macmillan, New York. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230608825_12
- [22]. Hossain, M., Atif, M., Ahmed, A. and Mia, L. (2020). Do LGBT workplace diversity policies create value for firms? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 167(4), pp.775-791.
- [23]. <http://www.kornferry.com/products/korn-ferry-leadership-architect/kfla-overview> [Accessed 22 March 2022].
- [24]. Inegbedion, H., Sunday, E., Asaleye, A., Lawal, A. and Adebajji, A. (2020). Managing diversity for organizational efficiency. *Sage Open*, 10(1), p.2158244019900173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019900173>
- [25]. Kammer, A., Azour, J., Selassie, A. A., Goldfajn, I., & Rhee, C. (2022). How war in Ukraine is reverberating across world's regions. *Washington: IMF, March 15, 2022*.
- [26]. Klarsfeld, A., Knappert, L., Kornau, A., Ngunjiri, F.W. and Sieben, B. (2019). Diversity in under-researched countries: new empirical fields challenging old theories? *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EDI-03-2019-0110>
- [27]. Koellen, T. (2021). Diversity management: A critical review and agenda for the future. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 30(3), pp.259-272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1056492619868025>
- [28]. Köllen, T. (2021). Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity in the Workplace. In *Handbook of Labor, Human Resources and Population Economics* (pp. 1-15). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- [29]. Kuknor, S., & Bhattacharya, S. (2021). Organizational inclusion and leadership in times of global crisis. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 15(1), 93-112. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v15i1.7>
- [30]. Kulik, C. T. (2022). We need a hero: HR and the 'next normal' workplace. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 32(1), 216-231. <https://doi:10.1111/1748-8583.12387>
- [31]. Ladwig, R.C. (2021). The Significance of Awareness about Gender Diversity for the Future of Work: A Multi-method Study of Organizational Structures and Policies Considering Trans and Gender Diversity. In *Conference Proceedings, Montreal Canada August* (Vol. 5, p. 06).
- [32]. Lashitew, A.A., Bals, L. and van Tulder, R. (2020). Inclusive business at the base of the pyramid: The role of embeddedness for enabling social innovations. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 162(2), pp.421-448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-018-3995-y>
- [33]. Lebriez, H., Esch, M., Wald, A., & Heinzelmann, R. (2019). What does Integrated Reporting mean for the value-relevance of environmental, social, and governmental performance? *Beta*, 33(2), 178-194.
- [34]. Lens, I. (2021). Equity and. Li, Y., Gong, M., Zhang, X.Y. and Koh, L.(2018). The impact of environmental, social, and governance disclosure on firm value: The role of CEO power. *The British Accounting Review*, 50(1), pp.60-75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2017.09.007>
- [35]. Mahmoud, A. B., Fuxman, L., Mohr, I., Reisel, W. D., & Grigoriou, N. (2021). "We aren't your reincarnation!" workplace motivation across X, Y and Z generations. *International Journal of Manpower*, 42(1), 193-209. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-09-2019-0448>
- [36]. Martinescu, E., Jansen, W., & Beersma, B. (2021). Negative gossip decreases targets' organizational citizenship behavior by decreasing social inclusion. A multi-method approaches. *Group & Organization Management*, 46(3), 463-497. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1059601120986876>
- [37]. Nkomo, S. M., Bell, M. P., Roberts, L. M., Joshi, A., & Thatcher, S. M. (2019). Diversity at a critical juncture: new theories for a complex phenomenon. *Academy of Management Review*, 44(3), 498-517. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2019.0103>
- [38]. Ohunakin, F., Adeniji, A., Ogunnaiké, O.O., Igbadume, F. and Akintayo, D.I. (2019). The effects of diversity management and inclusion on organisational outcomes: a case of multinational corporation. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 20(3), pp.93-102. <https://doi.org/10.3846/btp.2019.09>
- [39]. Padamsee, X. and Crowe, B. (2017). Unrealized Impact.
- [40]. Phan, T. T. H., Tran, H. X., Le, T. T., Nguyen, N., Pervan, S., & Tran, M. D. (2020). The relationship between sustainable development practices and financial performance: A case study of textile firms in Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 12(15), 5930.
- [41]. Putman, S. M., & Byker, E. J. (2020). Global citizenship 1-2-3: Learn, think, and act. *Kappa Delta Pi Record*, 56(1), 16-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00228958.2020.1696088>

- [42]. Rabaya, A. J., & Saleh, N. M. (2022). The moderating effect of IR framework adoption on the relationship between environmental, social, and governance (ESG) disclosure and a firm's competitive advantage. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(2), 2037-2055.
- [43]. Roberts, L. M., and Washington, E. F. (2020, June 1). U.S. Businesses must take meaningful action against racism. *Harvard Business Review*, pp.2-8. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2020/06/u-s-businesses-must-take-meaningful-action-against-racism>. Accessed March 30, 2022.
- [44]. Rosenkranz, K.M., Arora, T.K., Termuhlen, P.M., S.C., Misra, S., Dent, D. and Nfonsam, V., (2021). Diversity, equity and inclusion in medicine: why it matters and how do we achieve it? *Journal of surgical education*, 78(4), pp.1058-1065. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2020.11.013>
- [45]. Setati, S.T., Zhuwao, S., Ngirande, H. and Ndlovu, W. (2019). Gender diversity, ethnic diversity and employee performance in a South African higher education institution. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(1), pp.1-8. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v17i0.1061>
- [46]. Sherman, P. D. (2017). *The emergent global citizen: Cultivating global citizenship identity and engagement within Soka education*. Lancaster University (United Kingdom).
- [47]. Shore, L. M., Chung-Herrera, B. G., Dean, M. A., Ehrhart, K. H., Jung, D. I., Randel, A. E., & Singh, G. (2009). Diversity in organizations: Where are we now and where are we going? *Human resource management review*, 19(2), 117-133.
- [48]. Shore, L.M., Cleveland, J.N. and Sanchez, D. (2018). Inclusive workplaces: review and model. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28(2), pp.176-189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2017.07.003>
- [49]. Trivellas, P., Rafailidis, A., Polychroniou, P., & Dekoulou, P. (2018). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) and its internal consequences on job performance: The influence of corporate ethical values. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQSS-12-2017-0117>
- [50]. Velasco, M. and Sansone, C. (2019). Resistance to diversity and inclusion change initiatives: Strategies for transformational leaders. *Organization Development Journal*, 37(3), pp.9-20.
- [51]. Vitolla, F., Raimo, N., & Rubino, M. (2019). Intellectual capital disclosure and firm performance: an empirical analysis through integrated reporting. In *7th International OFEL Conference on Governance, Management and Entrepreneurship: Embracing Diversity in Organisations. April 5th-6th, 2019, Dubrovnik, Croatia* (pp. 245-255). Zagreb: Governance Research and Development Centre (CIRU).
- [52]. Warner, U. and Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik, J.H. (2003). Advances in cross-national comparison.
- [53]. Will, P. and Hamilton, O., (2021). *Is political correctness holding back progress on diversity, equity, and inclusion? LSE Business Review*. <http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/112268/> (Accessed 12 April 2022).
- [54]. World Bank. (2022). *The World Bank Annual Report 2022*. The World Bank.
- [55]. World Bank, 2019. *World Development Report (2019): The Changing Nature of Work*. World Development Report; Washington, DC: World Bank. © World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/30435> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO